

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

2026-YIL

IYUN/6-SON, III-QISM

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

*Elektron nashr. 2026-yil, iyun.
III-qism*

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Maxmudov Nosir, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Musayeva Shoirazimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor
Ali Konak (Ali Ko'nak), iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor (Turkiya)
Cham Tat Huei, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), professor (Malayziya)
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldix'ja o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dots.
Faxridinov Zafarjon Faxridin o'g'li, O'zb. Res. Bosh prokuraturasi HIJQKD boshqarma boshlig'i
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Anijon viloyati prokurorining o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farkhod, O'zb. Res. Bosh prokuraturasi IJQK Departamentining Namangan viloyati boshqarmasi boshlig'i
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), katta o'qituvchi
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), v.b. dots.
Djudi Smetana, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Krissi Lyuis, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (Moskva)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) (Turkiya)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon o'g'li, TDIU ITI departamenti rahbari
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent.
Abdulkarimova Dinara Rustamxonovna, bank-moliya akademiyasi professori, DSc., professor.
Ikramov Murod Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Nazarova Ra'no Rustamovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

Salimov Okil Umrzokovich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjavevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate
Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society
Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhridinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences
Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor
Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor
Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)
Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)
Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Fakhriddinov Zafarjon Fakhriddin ogli, Head of the DCEC under the Prosecutor General's Office of the Rep. of Uzb.
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Prosecutor of Anijan Region
Ochilov Farkhod, Head of the Namangan Regional Department of the Department of Internal Affairs of Rep. of Uzb.
Buzrukkhonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences
Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor
Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Glazova Marina Victorovna, Doctor of Sciences in Economics (Moscow)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE
Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor.
Abdukarimova Dinara Rustamkhanovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Ikramov Murod Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Nazarova Ra'no Rustamovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Geografiya fanlari doktori, professori
Umirzoqov Ja'sur Artiqboy o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent
Zebo Kuldasheva, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Doctor of Geographical Sciences, Professor
Umirzokov Jasur Artiqboy ugli, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor
Zebo Kuldasheva, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti,
O'zbekiston Respublikasi Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi Iqtisodiy
jinoyatlarga qarshi kurashish departamenti

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va
taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi
Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar
vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy
attestatsiya komissiyasi
rayosatining
2023-yil 1-apreldagi
336/3-sonli qarori bilan
ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

SUD BOSHQARUVCHILARI FAOLIYATINING IQTISODIY RAG'BATLANTIRISH TIZIMI VA ULARNING SUBSIDIAR JAVOBGARLIGI: MUAMMOLAR VA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI	12
Soliyev Damirjon Nurmatovich	
BLOKCHEYN TEKNOLOGIYASI ASOSIDA MOLIVAVIY TRANZAKSIYALARNI NAZORAT QILISH TIZIMI (SMART-KONTRAKTLAR, MARKAZLASHMAGAN MA'LUMOTLAR BAZASI VA AUDIT IZLARI)	18
Olimova Mukhlisa Vohidjon qizi	
SANOAT SEKTORIDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISH: STRATEGIK AFZALLIKLAR VA TO'SIQLAR TAHLILI	26
Xatamov Ochildi Qurbonovich	
ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ БАНКОВСКОЙ СИСТЕМЫ УЗБЕКИСТАНА КАК ФАКТОР ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЕЁ КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТИ	32
PhD. Юлдашева С.Ш	
TREND MODELLARI YORDAMIDA MEHNAT RESURSLARI SONINI EKONOMETRIK MODELLASHTIRISH	38
Haydarova Dinora Atamurot qizi	
МЕТОДОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ ВЫКУПА И ПРОДАЖИ КВОТ НА ОРОСИТЕЛЬНУЮ ВОДУ	43
Гоженко Борис Владимирович	
MOLIVAVIY LEVERIJ SAMARASI VA QARZ MABLAG'LARINI BOSHQARISHDA UNDA FOYDALANISH	50
Latipova Shaxnoza Maxmudovna	
XIZMATLAR SOHASIDA WEBMONEY TO'LOV TIZIMINI KOMPYUTERDA O'RNATISH VA SOZLASHNING IQTISODIYOTDAGI ROLI	55
Fazilat Esirgapovna Jomonqulova	
Nizomov Murod	
Qurbonboyeva Rayhon Bahronjon qizi	
MECHANISMS FOR THE FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE	58
Shukhrat Mashrabboevich Mamadaliyev	
BANK SEKTORIDA OPERATSION SAMARADORLIK VA XAVFLARNI BOSHQARISHNI BAHOLASH	62
R.I.Rashidov	
A.N. Elmurodov	
A.A. Muhiddinov	
TRANSFORMING ECONOMIC GOVERNANCE IN UZBEKISTAN THROUGH DIGITAL PUBLIC SECTOR TOOLS	68
Bokhodirov Boriykhon Boburovich	
Bahromjon Urmanov	
TIJORAT BANKLARINING INVESTITSIYA VA KREDIT SALOHİYATINI BOSHQARISH	74
Ergashova Nilufar Sobirovna	
DEHQON XO'JALIKLARIDA QO'SHILGAN QIYMAT ZANJIRINING SHAKLLANISHI VA UNGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR	80
Azizov Shohsuvor Yuldashevich	
VERTIKAL INTEGRATSİYALASHGAN BANK TUZILMASINI "YAGONA MFO" TEKNOLOGIYASI ASOSIDA TRANSFORMATSIYA QILISH SXEMASI	84
Qo'shboqov Doniyorbek Maxramqulovich	

O'ZBEKISTON SANOAT KORXONALARIDA "YASHIL EKOTIZIM" VA RESURS SAMARADORLIGI (RECP)NI JORIY ETISHNING METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI HAMDA EMISSIALARNI KAMAYTIRISH SAMARADORLIGI.....	90
Do'stqobilov Ulug'bek Ibrohimovich	
TURIZM SOHASIDA OILAVIY TADBIRKORLIK TUSHUNCHALARINING MAZMUN VA MOHIYATIGA ILMIY-NAZARIY YONDASHUVLAR	94
Pardayeva Ozoda Mamayunusovna	
СНИЖЕНИЕ ТЕХНИЧЕСКИХ И КОММЕРЧЕСКИХ ПОТЕРЬ ЭЛЕКТРОЭНЕРГИИ КАК НАПРАВЛЕНИЕ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ РАСПРЕДЕЛИТЕЛЬНЫХ СЕТЕЙ УЗБЕКИСТАНА	100
Маърупова Дилсора Абдулла кизи	
O'ZBEKISTON QURILISH SOHASIDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA VA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISHNING INSTITUTIONAL SHART-SHAROITLARI.....	105
Qodirov Sardorbek Isroiljon o'g'li	
АКАДЕМИЧЕСКИЕ НАВЫКИ И ОСОБЕННОСТИ ИХ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ	113
Усманова Зумрад Исламовна	
Рахматуллаев Алижон	
Сайфитдинов Азизжон	
G'AZNACHILIK OPERATSIYALARINING BANKLIKVIDLIGINI TA'MINLASHDAGI O'RNI (SILICON VALLEY BANK MISOLIDA).....	119
Axadov Shahboz Shuxrat o'g'li	
ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ СИСТЕМЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ТВЁРДЫМИ БЫТОВЫМИ ОТХОДАМИ В Г. ТАШКЕНТЕ: ОТ ПОЛИГОННОГО ЗАХОРОНЕНИЯ К РЕСУРСНО-ЭНЕРГЕТИЧЕСКОМУ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЮ	127
Джусупов Кубанычбек	
STRATEGIK BOSHQARUV HISOBI AXBOROT TA'MINOTINING METODOLOGIK ASOSLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	133
Umidjon Kostayev	
DEVELOPMENT OF A METHODOLOGY FOR TEACHING STUDENTS OBJECTORIENTED PROGRAMMING IN A VIRTUAL COLLABORATIVE ENVIRONMENT USING GENERATIVE ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TOOLS	140
Saidova Dilfuza Ergashovna	
AUDIT SIFATI NAZORATINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	145
Muydinov Erkin Jamaldinovich	
THE ROLE OF E-COMMERCE IN ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN'S DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION.....	152
Shakhriddinova Sitora Tolibjon kizi	
THE IMPACT OF SUSTAINABILITY PRACTICES IN THE AGRICULTURAL INDUSTRY IN UZBEKISTAN.....	157
Yorkin Ziyodullaev	
Munisa Bekmirzaeva	
РОЛЬ ЦИРКУЛЯРНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ В ЗЕЛЕНОМ РОСТЕ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	166
Мохамед Эйд Али Балбаа	
Усманова Азиза Алишеровна	
OZIQ-OVQAT SANOATI KORXONALARIDA SAMARADORLIKNI OSHIRISHNING INNOVATSION YO'LLARI.....	173
Shakirxodjaeva Zuxraxon Rustamxanovna	
BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH HISOBOTLARINI TUZISH MASALALARI: XALQARO TAJRIBA VA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI.....	180
Menglikulov Baxtiyor Yusupovich	

THE IMPACT OF SUSTAINABILITY PRACTICES IN THE AGRICULTURAL INDUSTRY IN UZBEKISTAN	184
Yorkin Ziyodullaev	
Munisa Bekmirzaeva	
TASTE OF PLACE: HOW LOCAL-INGREDIENT SOURCING AFFECTS GUEST SATISFACTION AND MENU PROFITABILITY IN HOTEL RESTAURANTS	193
Bahodirova Durdona	
Atametova Sevara	
INTERACTIONS IN CREATIVE TOURISM: RESIDENTS' PERSPECTIVES IN UZBEKISTAN.....	198
Dildora Khodjaeva Mukhamedkhodjaevna	
Jasmin Raxmidinova	
XO'JALIK YURITUVCHISUBYEKTLARNING LIKVIDLILIGINI TA'MINLASH MASALALARI	204
Bauyetdinov M.J.	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISH SHAROITIDA MINTAQA TABIIY RESURSLARIDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH YO'LLARI (BUXORO VILOYATI MISOLIDA)	212
Safarov Otabek Abduhamidovich	
SANOAT KORXONALARIDA INNOVATSION FAOLIYAT SAMARADORLIGINING NAZARIY JIHATLARI.....	218
O'rinov Akmaljon Axmadjonovich	
ТЕОРИИ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ФИНАНСОВЫМИ РИСКАМИ В БАНКОВСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ.....	223
Убайдуллаева Мафтунахон Акмалхон кизи	
SURXONDARYO VILOYATI IQTISODIYOTIGA JALB ETILAYOTGAN INVESTITSİYALAR SAMARADORLIGI TAHLILI	230
Xatamova Manzura Ochildiyevna	
TURISTIK MAHSULOT MARKETINGI: NAZARIY ASOSLARI VA RIVOJLANTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI	240
Usmanova Zumrad Islamovna	
IN VITRO TEXNOLOGIYASI ASOSIDA KARTOSHKA URUG'CHILIGI ZANJIRI SAMARADORLIGINI IQTISODIY BAHOLASHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI	244
Mardonova Zarifa Numonjonovna	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA KREDIT OPERATSIYALARI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH UCHUN RESURSLAR YETARLILIGINI TA'MINLASH MASALALARI	251
Sheraliyev Olimjon O'ktam o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTONDA ESG MOLIYALASHTIRISH TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI VA MEXANIZMLARI	258
Ajibayeva Raiya Maxsutovna	
YASHIL MOLIYALASHTIRISH INSTRUMENTLARI ORQALI BARQAROR IQTISODIY O'SISHNI TA'MINLASH MASALALARI	262
Ajibayeva Raiya Maxsutovna	
ANIQ FANLARNI O'QITISHDA METAKOGNITIV YONDASHUVLAR: TEORETIK ASOSLAR, KOGNITIV ARHITEKTURA VA AMALIY TRANSFER MUAMMOLARI	265
Namozov Diyorbek Baxtiyor o'g'li	
XUFYONA IQTISODIYOTNING MOHIYATI VA UNI O'ZBEKISTONDA KAMAYTIRISH CHORA-TADBIRLARI	270
Kalandarov R.A.	
RAQAMLI TO'LOV TIZIMLARIDA ALOQA OPERATORLARI ROLINI OSHIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	276
Nuraliyev Nurbek Rustam o'g'li	
DAVLAT BUDJETI DAROMADLARI BARQARORLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA BILVOSITA SOLIQQA TORTISHNING ASOSIY YO'NALISHLARI	281
Mansurova Arofatxon Shavkat qizi	

INTERNATIONAL TRENDS AND THE LEGAL FRAMEWORK OF E-COMMERCE DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN.....	286
Usmanova Zumrad Islamovna	

INTERNATIONAL TRENDS AND THE LEGAL FRAMEWORK OF E-COMMERCE DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN

Usmanova Zumrad Islamovna

Associate Professor of the Department of Marketing,
Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service

E-mail: usmanovazumrad793@gmail.com

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0006-0283-9645>

Abstract. The article examines the impact of international economic integration, globalization, and digital transformation on the development of e-commerce in Uzbekistan. The study analyzes the main trends of regionalization and international economic cooperation that shape the modern global business environment. Particular attention is paid to the role of information and communication technologies in transforming traditional business models and creating new opportunities for electronic commerce. The research highlights the evolution of e-commerce in Uzbekistan, from the emergence of the first online stores in the early 2000s to the formation of a rapidly growing digital ecosystem encompassing online retail, electronic payments, digital marketing, supply chain management, and electronic data exchange. Using a qualitative analytical approach, the study evaluates the factors contributing to the expansion of e-commerce and identifies existing challenges related to legal regulation, cybersecurity, consumer protection, and digital infrastructure. The findings indicate that Uzbekistan has achieved notable progress in developing the digital economy through ongoing reforms and technological modernization. However, further improvements in the regulatory framework, digital literacy, cybersecurity, and international cooperation are necessary to enhance the competitiveness and sustainability of the national e-commerce sector. The article concludes with practical recommendations aimed at strengthening Uzbekistan's integration into the global digital economy and promoting the long-term development of electronic commerce.

Keywords: e-commerce, digital economy, globalization, international economic integration, regionalization, digital transformation, information technologies, electronic payments, cybersecurity, Uzbekistan, legal framework, digital infrastructure, online business, economic development.

Annotatsiya. Maqolada xalqaro iqtisodiy integratsiya, globallashuv va raqamli transformatsiyaning O'zbekistonda elektron tijorat rivojlanishiga ta'siri o'rganiladi. Tadqiqotda zamonaviy global biznes muhitini shakllantiruvchi mintaqaviylashuv va xalqaro iqtisodiy hamkorlikning asosiy tendensiyalari tahlil qilingan. An'anaviy biznes modellarini transformatsiya qilish hamda elektron tijorat uchun yangi imkoniyatlar yaratishda axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarining roliga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan. Tadqiqotda O'zbekistonda elektron tijoratning rivojlanish bosqichlari, ya'ni 2000-yillarning boshlarida ilk internet-do'konlarning paydo bo'lishidan tortib, onlayn chakana savdo, elektron to'lovlar, raqamli marketing, ta'minot zanjirini boshqarish va elektron ma'lumotlar almashinuvini qamrab olgan jadal rivojlanayotgan raqamli ekotizim shakllanishigacha bo'lgan jarayon yoritilgan. Sifat jihatidan tahliliy yondashuv asosida tadqiqotda elektron tijorat kengayishiga ta'sir etuvchi omillar baholanib, huquqiy tartibga solish, kiberxavfsizlik, iste'molchilar huquqlarini himoya qilish va raqamli infratuzilma bilan bog'liq mavjud muammolar aniqlangan. Tadqiqot natijalari O'zbekistonda keng qamrovli islohotlar va texnologik modernizatsiya orqali raqamli iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirish borasida sezilarli yutuqlarga erishilganini ko'rsatadi. Shu bilan birga, milliy elektron tijorat sektorining raqobatbardoshligi va barqarorligini oshirish uchun me'yoriy-huquqiy bazani, raqamli savodxonlikni, kiberxavfsizlikni hamda xalqaro hamkorlikni yanada takomillashtirish zarur. Maqola O'zbekistonning global raqamli iqtisodiyotga integratsiyasini kuchaytirish va elektron tijoratning uzoq muddatli rivojlanishini rag'batlantirishga qaratilgan amaliy tavsiyalar bilan yakunlanadi.

Kalitso'zlar: elektrontijorat, raqamli iqtisodiyot, globallashuv, xalqaro iqtisodiy integratsiya, mintaqaviylashuv, raqamli transformatsiya, axborot texnologiyalari, elektron to'lovlar, kiberxavfsizlik, O'zbekiston, huquqiy baza, raqamli infratuzilma, onlayn biznes, iqtisodiy rivojlanish.

Аннотация. В статье рассматривается влияние международной экономической интеграции, глобализации и цифровой трансформации на развитие электронной коммерции в Узбекистане. В исследовании анализируются основные тенденции регионализации и международного экономического

сотрудничества, формирующие современную глобальную бизнес-среду. Особое внимание уделяется роли информационно-коммуникационных технологий в трансформации традиционных бизнес-моделей и создании новых возможностей для электронной коммерции. В работе освещается эволюция электронной коммерции в Узбекистане — от появления первых интернет-магазинов в начале 2000-х годов до формирования динамично развивающейся цифровой экосистемы, охватывающей онлайн-розницу, электронные платежи, цифровой маркетинг, управление цепями поставок и электронный обмен данными. На основе качественного аналитического подхода в исследовании оцениваются факторы, способствующие расширению электронной коммерции, а также выявляются существующие проблемы, связанные с правовым регулированием, кибербезопасностью, защитой прав потребителей и цифровой инфраструктурой. Результаты исследования показывают, что Узбекистан достиг значительного прогресса в развитии цифровой экономики благодаря комплексным реформам и технологической модернизации. Вместе с тем для повышения конкурентоспособности и устойчивости национального сектора электронной коммерции необходимо дальнейшее совершенствование нормативно-правовой базы, цифровой грамотности, кибербезопасности и международного сотрудничества. Статья завершается практическими рекомендациями, направленными на укрепление интеграции Узбекистана в глобальную цифровую экономику и обеспечение долгосрочного развития электронной коммерции.

Ключевые слова: электронная коммерция, цифровая экономика, глобализация, международная экономическая интеграция, регионализация, цифровая трансформация, информационные технологии, электронные платежи, кибербезопасность, Узбекистан, правовая база, цифровая инфраструктура, онлайн-бизнес, экономическое развитие.

INTRODUCTION

The contemporary global economy is characterized by intensive processes of economic globalization and international integration. These processes manifest themselves through the increasing interaction of national economies, the internationalization of economic activities, and the gradual convergence toward common economic standards and norms. International integration has become one of the defining features of modern economic development, influencing trade relations, investment flows, technological exchange, and institutional reforms worldwide.

Regionalization serves as an important component of international economic integration. Major regional economic blocs such as the European Union (EU), the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN), and the North American economic area demonstrate how countries seek to enhance economic cooperation through various forms of integration. Developing and transition economies have also become increasingly active participants in these processes. In the post-Soviet region, integration initiatives within the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS) have significantly influenced economic development strategies.

At the same time, rapid advances in information and communication technologies have transformed traditional business models and created new opportunities for economic interaction. E-commerce has emerged as one of the most dynamic sectors of the digital economy, fundamentally changing the ways goods and services are produced, marketed, and distributed. In Uzbekistan, the development of e-commerce has become a strategic priority within the broader agenda of digital transformation and economic modernization.

This study examines international trends influencing e-commerce development and analyzes the legal and economic framework supporting the growth of e-commerce in Uzbekistan.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The phenomenon of international economic integration has long attracted the attention of economists and policymakers. Numerous studies emphasize that regionalization contributes to the optimization of international trade, investment flows, and the movement of capital and labor. Scholars argue that integration processes create favorable conditions for sustainable economic growth, increased competitiveness, and the development of innovation-driven economies.

Theoretical approaches to regionalization highlight the gradual progression from free trade agreements and customs unions to common markets and monetary unions. These stages reflect increasing levels of economic interdependence and institutional cooperation among participating countries. Research also demonstrates that successful integration depends on factors such as geographic proximity, economic complementarity, historical ties, and political commitment.

In the field of digital economy studies, researchers emphasize the transformative role of information and communication technologies in reshaping business processes. According to S. Kovalev [1], modern enterprises increasingly rely on digital technologies to optimize organizational structures, improve business processes, and enhance market competitiveness. E-commerce represents one of the most significant manifestations of digital transformation, integrating online marketing, electronic payment systems, supply chain management, inventory control, and data exchange technologies.

Recent studies on developing economies indicate that government support, regulatory frameworks, digital infrastructure, and consumer trust are critical determinants of e-commerce growth. These factors are particularly important for countries undergoing economic modernization and digital transformation, such as Uzbekistan.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research employs a qualitative analytical approach based on the examination of international economic integration theories, regionalization processes, and the development of e-commerce ecosystems. The study utilizes comparative analysis to identify global trends influencing digital commerce and evaluates their relevance to Uzbekistan's economic environment.

The research is based on the review of academic literature, policy documents, and statistical observations related to international economic development and e-commerce expansion. Special attention is given to the interaction between globalization processes, technological innovation, and national regulatory frameworks that facilitate digital business activities.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The analysis demonstrates that international economic integration and digitalization are mutually reinforcing processes. Regional economic cooperation creates favorable conditions for cross-border trade and investment, while digital technologies facilitate efficient economic interactions beyond traditional geographic limitations.

Global experience shows that successful e-commerce ecosystems require a combination of technological infrastructure, supportive legal frameworks, secure payment systems, and effective logistics networks. Countries that have invested in digital transformation have achieved significant improvements in business efficiency and consumer accessibility.

In Uzbekistan, e-commerce development has evolved through several stages. The first phase began in the early 2000s with the emergence of online stores primarily specializing in electronics, computers, and household appliances. During this period, internet penetration remained limited, and online commerce represented only a small segment of economic activity.

The second phase was characterized by increasing internet accessibility, improvements in telecommunications infrastructure, and growing public awareness of digital services. Government initiatives aimed at supporting information technologies and digital entrepreneurship contributed to the expansion of electronic commerce.

Currently, Uzbekistan is experiencing accelerated growth in e-commerce as part of its broader digital economy strategy. Modern e-commerce in the country encompasses not only online retail transactions but also integrated business processes such as electronic payments, digital marketing, supply chain management, inventory control, electronic data interchange, and cloud-based information storage systems.

The findings indicate that Uzbekistan's e-commerce sector benefits from ongoing economic reforms and digitalization policies. Nevertheless, several challenges remain, including the need to strengthen consumer protection mechanisms, improve cybersecurity standards, expand digital literacy, and further develop legal regulations governing electronic transactions.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The study confirms that globalization, regionalization, and technological innovation are key drivers of e-commerce development in modern economies. International integration creates favorable conditions for economic cooperation and digital trade, while advances in information technologies enable new forms of business activity and market participation.

The development of e-commerce in Uzbekistan reflects broader international trends and demonstrates significant potential for future growth. The country has gradually strengthened the foundations of the digital economy through infrastructure development, technological modernization, and regulatory reforms.

To further enhance the effectiveness and competitiveness of Uzbekistan's e-commerce sector, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Strengthen the legal framework regulating electronic commerce, electronic contracts, and digital consumer rights.
2. Improve cybersecurity measures to ensure the protection of personal and financial data.
3. Expand digital infrastructure and internet accessibility across all regions of the country.
4. Promote digital literacy among businesses and consumers to increase confidence in online transactions.
5. Support innovation and entrepreneurship through incentives for technology-based enterprises and e-commerce platforms.
6. Enhance international cooperation and harmonization of digital trade regulations to facilitate cross-border e-commerce activities.
7. Develop advanced electronic payment systems and logistics networks to improve transaction efficiency and delivery reliability.

The effective implementation of these measures may contribute to the sustainable development of e-commerce in Uzbekistan and support its integration into the global digital economy.

REFERENCES

1. Kovalev, S. M., & Kovalev, V. M. (2014). *Secrets of successful enterprises: Business processes and organizational structure*. Moscow: BITEK.
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-6079. (2020). On Approval of the Strategy "Digital Uzbekistan — 2030" and Measures for Its Effective Implementation. Adopted on October 5, 2020. <https://lex.uz/docs/-5030957>
3. Balassa, B. (1961). *The Theory of Economic Integration*. Homewood, Illinois: Richard D. Irwin.
4. Laudon, K. C., & Traver, C. G. (2024). *E-commerce 2023–2024: Business, Technology, Society*. 18th ed. Harlow: Pearson Education Limited.
5. World Trade Organization. (2018). *World Trade Report 2018: The Future of World Trade: How Digital Technologies Are Transforming Global Commerce*. Geneva: WTO.
6. United Nations Conference on Trade and Development. (2021). *Digital Economy Report 2021: Cross-border Data Flows and Development: For Whom the Data Flow*. Geneva: United Nations.
7. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. LRU-792. (2022). On Electronic Commerce. Adopted on September 29, 2022.

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz HAKIMOV

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Hasan MAQSUDOV

2026. № 6/3

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin. Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

EI.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, @iqtisodiyot_77 telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>